

SCIENCE VIRTUAL MODULE IN APLAYA NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL -ANNEX STA. ROSA CITY, LAGUNA: BASIS FOR SUPPLEMENTARY ONLINE ACTIVITIES

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ABSTRACT

One of the distance learning delivery modalities implemented among the public and private schools in the country is online distance learning. Online learning enables multiple forms of interaction and dialogue that can bridge the distance between teachers and students it provides access to a vast array of interactive and multimedia learning resources that can be used to design learning environments for learners in different circumstances. Hence, this study aimed to determine how online students accomplish the Grade 10 science virtual module in Aplaya National High School-Annex. The descriptive analysis method was used in the study. Data were gathered from 100 grade 10 students' respondents using a researcher-made survey questionnaire. The percentage and frequency, weighted mean, ANOVA and Pearson R were tools used in analyzing the data. Results showed that the demographic characteristics of the students such as age, sex, did not show any significant relationship on how students accomplish science virtual activities both in the synchronous and asynchronous class. Moreover, there is no significant difference between the virtual activities in science virtual module in terms of the three identified competencies both in the synchronous and asynchronous class. The result of the study found that most learners were very effective in their learning strategies. for every synchronous and asynchronous virtual activities in online distance learning. Despite variations in the activities between synchronous and asynchronous, students accomplished virtual activities in science online class Perhaps the reason for the result is the attitude of the student towards the importance of learning.

Keywords: Virtual Activity, Synchronous, Asynchronous, Distance Learning, Supplementary Learning Activities

INTRODUCTION

Online learning content is accessible through different kinds text, images, sounds, and artefacts, and forms of media adaptive, interactive, narrative, productive The informed user can employ various online learning resources to create a learning environment that suits his personal learning needs e.g. learning styles, individual accessibility needs, motivation, etc. In addition to the knowledge of different types of ICT, it is important to understand someone's personal learning needs. (Lebenicnik et al 2015). Furthermore, Online learning can be termed as a tool that can make the teaching–learning process more student-centered, more innovative, and even more flexible. Online learning is defined as “learning experiences in synchronous or asynchronous environments using different devices (e.g., mobile phones, laptops, etc.) with internet access. In these environments, students can be anywhere (independent) to learn and interact with instructors and other students” (Singh and Thurman, 2019). The synchronous learning environment is structured in the sense that students attend live lectures, there are real-time interactions between educators and learners, and there is a possibility of instant feedback, whereas asynchronous learning environments are not properly structured. In such a learning environment, learning content is not available in the form of live lectures or classes; it is available at different learning systems and forums. Instant feedback and immediate response are not possible under such an environment (Littlefield, 2018).

Online learning enables multiple forms of interaction and dialogue that can bridge the distance between teachers and learners Anderson, Calvert, Garrison as cited by Arinto (2017). and provide access to a vast array of interactive and multimedia learning resources that can be used to design learning environments for learners in different circumstances. With regards to its learning resources infrastructure or technical requirements utilized in ODL, the memorandum suggested the following to be used, but not limited to the self-learning modules (SLMs), textbooks (TXs), Primer Lessons, activity sheets, teacher-made videos and other supplementary learning materials, and Open Educational Resources (OERs). Since it is in online, self-learning modules and Primer Lessons was converted into different digital content formats such as video/audio lessons, interactive/inclusive electronic SLMs (e-SLMs) and made available through the DepEd Learning Resources Portal, DepEd Commons, DepEd Learning Management System (LMS) and/or different DepEd recognized LMS, such as Edmodo, Google Classroom, Schoology, The Modular Object-Oriented Dynamic Learning Environment (Moodle) and other available LMSs that may be used as long as there is a software that allows the school to administer, document, track, and record the progress of the learners and ensuring the appropriateness of learning management system or educational platform in the delivery of instruction. In its reiteration, open-source LMS must be user-friendly to be able to execute a variety of functions that work together to provide a seamless experience for both teachers and learners.

Courtney & Mathews (2015) presented an overview of the evolution of distance learning with a particular emphasis on current models and emerging methods of instruction for online learners. Further, schools implementing ODL may adopt a combination of synchronous and asynchronous online teaching. Synchronous learning is

online or distance education that happens in real time, often with a set class schedule and required login times. In the provided guidelines, Synchronous learning shall be conducted using live webinars, video conferencing, live chat or instant messaging. Teachers are highly encouraged to use Google Meet to record a specific activity especially for performance task-based output

Research Questions

The study aims to determine the Science Virtual Module for Grade 10 Aplaya National High School-Annex Sta. Rosa City, Laguna: Basis for Supplementary Online Activities. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Students
 - 1.1.1. Age
 - 1.1.2. Sex
 2. How do the students accomplish the virtual activities for second quarter in terms of:
 - 2.1 Synchronous
 - 2.2 Asynchronous
 3. What Supplementary Online Activities may be developed?
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METHODOLOGY

The study used a descriptive survey research design. Sukamolson as cited by Apuke (2017) defined descriptive survey research as a method of measuring the characteristics of a group to understand their behavior and/or characteristics. This design is concerned with examining a certain condition or situation using appropriate statistical tools.

The design is deemed appropriate for the study as it aims to determine the science virtual module for Grade 10 in Aplaya National High School-Annex Sta. Rosa City, Laguna as basis for supplementary online activities for synchronous and asynchronous online learning.

The study covered ten sections of Grade 10 students under online distance learning modality in Aplaya National High School Annex (APEX) in the Division of Santa Rosa City. The researcher randomly selected the participants for every section. 100 students out of 100 students 10 students from the respective sections of Matipid, Mapitagan, Matiyaga, Mapagmahal and Matapat. were chosen to answer the questionnaire. The researcher is the science teacher of grade 10 under online distance learning. The first part presents the profile of the participants according to demographic variables age, sex, and grades for second quarter. The second part deals with the mean scores on the virtual activities; while the third part looks into the significant differences and relationship of the variables under study.

The instrument to be used in the study is a survey questionnaire. It will be developed based on the literature review and readings. The questionnaire will be divided into two parts. The first part is about the personal data of the participants; while the second part will determine how the students accomplish virtual activities during synchronous and asynchronous online sessions. The responses will be determined using a 5-point Likert Scale.

Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.50 - 5.00	Always (Daily/everyday)
4	3.50 - 4.49	Often (4 times a week)
3	2.50 - 3.49	Sometimes (2 times a week)
2	1.50 - 2.49	Seldom (Once a week)
1	1.00 - 1.49	Never (Never)

The instrument will undergo a dry-run for validation purposes. The results of the dry-run will serve as the basis for revising and improving the instrument before its actual administration.

The survey was administered using Google Form. Students received an invitation to participate in the survey by email and were free to participate in the survey. Students were given one week to complete the survey. After the deadline, the researchers developed a summary of the survey findings and sent this summary to the students who had completed the survey.

A request letter for approval will be sent to the principal or school head of Aplaya National High School Annex (APEX) in the Division of Santa Rosa City, for the conduct of the study in the school. Upon approval, the researcher will distribute the questionnaires using Google Form and the online platform to the identified participants with the explanation of the purpose and aim of the said survey. Questions regarding the survey will be facilitated by the researcher. After answering the survey form, the results will be consolidated according to their responses to come up with the conclusion on the implementation and the barriers in the implementation of online distance learning. The data of the participants will be organized, tabulated, analyzed and presented in graphs and text format. The descriptive and inferential statistics like frequency distribution, percentage, weighted mean and ANOVA will be used to present the data gathered.

In addition, ethical considerations will then be part of this research work so that the participants will be protected with their data privacy. The participants will be informed through letters and e-mails that the collection of data will be done at a specified time without compromising their time in their school or office work. Furthermore, the identity of the participants in the entire study will be kept anonymous. Likewise, the data collected from the participants will be kept confidential.

The frequency distribution and percentage will be used to determine the demographic profile of participants. The weighted mean will be used to show the average score of how the participants accomplish virtual activities during synchronous and asynchronous online sessions. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) will be used to test the

significant difference on the virtual activities for second quarter in terms synchronous and asynchronous online learning Pearson R Coefficient of Correlation was used to determine the significant relationship between the student's profile and the virtual activities.

RESULTS

Table 1
Demographic Profile of Students Participants

Characteristics	F	%
1.1. <u>Age</u>		
15 years old	45	45
16 years old	49	49
17 years old	6	6
Total	100	100
1.2. <u>Sex</u>		
Male	49	49
Female	51	51
Total	100	100
<u>Grade for Second Quarter</u>		
91-100	21	21
81-90	56	56
76-80	19	19
75 and below	4	4
Total	100	100

Table 2
Mean Score on Science Virtual Activities in terms of
Competencies Week 5 Synchronous

<i>Week 5 Competency: Explain the effects of EM radiation on living things and the environment</i>	Student	
	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Review on the Effects of EM radiation on living things and the environment		
1.1 Study the previous topic related EM radiation	3.55	O
1.2 Highlight the important concept and information about the topic in the module	4.07	O
1.3 Answer review questions given by our teacher promptly	3.65	O
1.4 Write a summary of what I remember and learned about the topic	3.2	S

1.5 Present the things I learned about the topic using graphic organizers and/or illustrations (e.g. charts, tables, matrix, graphs etc.)	3.12	S
2. Lecture/Discussion on the Effect of EM radiation on living the environment		
2.1 Read the assigned topic about the in advance from the module.	3.05	S
2.2 Study the materials (e.g. video clips, power point presentations) uploaded/sent by our teacher in advance	3.88	O
2.3 Read other books and materials about the topic	3.02	S
2.4 Jot down notes and questions	3.67	O
2.5 Organize my notes using illustrations and/or graphic organizers	3.08	S
2.6 Note ideas, points, and concepts I do not understand and ask them to my teacher for clarification	3.2	S
3. Video Analysis on the Effects of EM radiation on living things and the environment		
3.1 Watch the video silently	4.38	A
3.2 Jots down notes and information about the topic;	3.86	O
3.3 Answer questions given by the teacher;	3.63	O
3.4 Participate during the discussion of the video	2.55	S
3.5 Ask questions about the video viewed	2.55	S
4. Close Reading Activity on the Effects of EM radiation on living things and the environment		
4.1 Read the assigned silently	4.31	A
4.2 Note/ highlight specific words or phrases found in the text	4.03	O
	3.08	S
4.3 Answer text-dependent/ comprehension questions based on my understanding of the text	3.32	S
4.4 Outline the content of the text using graphic organizers	4.46	A
4.5 Annotate the assigned text with main ideas, questions, or comments		
Average Mean	3.66	O

Table 3
Mean Score on Science Virtual Activities in terms of
Competencies Week 5 Asynchronous

Week 5 Competency: <i>Explain the effects of EM radiation on living things and the environment</i>	Student	
	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Activity Sheets based on the SLM on the effects of EM radiation		
1.1 Read the instructions in each activity carefully	3.55	O
1.2 Re-read the self-learning module	3.83	O
1.3 Review notes about the topic	3.41	O
1.4 Clarify misunderstood instructions and/or parts of the activity to the teacher	3.08	S
1.5 Check my answers against the given answer key/ key to correction included in the module	3.64	O
2. Performance Task: Provide Examples of useful instrument or devices that use EM waves; identify its advantages and disadvantages		
2.1 Re-read the self-learning module	4.26	A
2.2 Read and understand the instructions/ procedures in accomplishing the activity	3.58	O
2.3 Prepare a plan/timetable in accomplishing the performance task (e.g. checklist, calendar of activities)	3.91	O
2.4 Prepare needed materials for the activity	4.15	O
2.5 Read and understand the scoring guide before working on the task	3.84	O
Average Mean	4.08	O

Table 4
Mean Score on Science Virtual Activities in terms of
Competencies Week 6-7 Synchronous

Week 6 - 7 Competency: Predict the qualitative characteristics (orientation, type, and magnification) of images formed by plane and curved mirrors and lenses	Student	
	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Review on the qualitative characteristics of images formed by plane and curved mirrors and lenses	4.06	O
1.1 Study the previous topic related to qualitative characteristics of images formed by plane and curved mirrors and lenses	3.63	O

1.2 Highlight the important concept and information about the topic in the module		
1.3 Answer review questions given by our teacher promptly	3.26	S
1.4 Write a summary of what I remember and learned about the topic	2.87	S
1.5 Present the things I learned about the topic using graphic organizers and/or illustrations (e.g. charts, tables, matrix, graphs etc.)	3.14	S
2. Lecture/Discussion on the qualitative characteristics (orientation, type, and magnification) of images formed by plane and curved mirrors and lenses		
2.1 Read the assigned topic about the in advance from the module	3.88	O
2.2 Study the materials (e.g. video clips, Powerpoint presentations) uploaded/sent by our teacher in advance	2.87	S
2.3 Read other books and materials about the topic	3.69	O
2.4 Jot down notes and questions	2.96	S
2.5 Organize my notes using illustrations and/or graphic organizers	3.23	S
2.6 Note ideas, points, and concepts I do not understand and ask them to my teacher for clarification	4.39	A
3. Video Analysis on the qualitative characteristics of images formed by plane and curved mirrors and lenses		
3.1 Watch the video silently;	3.89	O
3.2 Jots down notes and information about the topic;	3.64	O
3.3 Answer questions given by the teacher;	3.64	O
3.4 Participate during the discussion of the video	2.79	S
3.5 Ask questions about the video viewed	4.25	A
4. Reading Activity on the qualitative characteristics of images formed by plane and curved mirrors and lenses		
4.1 Read the assigned silently	3.75	O
4.2 Note/ highlight specific words or phrases found in the text	3.85	O
4.3 Answer text-dependent/ comprehension questions based on my understanding of the text	2.99	S
	3.35	S
	4.42	A

4.4 Outline the content of the text using graphic organizers 4.5 Annotate the assigned text with main ideas, questions, or comments	
Average Mean	3.88 O

Table 5
Mean Score on Science Virtual Activities in terms of
Competencies Week 6-7 Asynchronous

Week 6 - 7 Competency: Predict the qualitative characteristics (orientation, type, and magnification) of images formed by plane and curved mirrors and lenses	Student	
	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Activity Sheets on the qualitative characteristics (orientation, type, and magnification) of images formed by plane and curved mirrors and lenses based from the SLM		
1.1 Read the instructions in each activity carefully	3.66	O
1.2 Re-read the self-learning module	3.65	O
1.3 Review notes about the topic	3.17	S
1.4 Clarify misunderstood instructions and/or parts of the activity to the teacher	2.97	S
1.5 Check my answers against the given answer key/ key to correction included in the module	3.78	O
2. Collaborative Activity: Create a video presentation of images produced by spherical mirrors and lenses and their uses in daily life		
2.1 Re-read the self-learning module	4.13	O
2.2 Read and understand the instructions/ procedures in accomplishing the collaborative activity	3.72	O
2.3 Prepare a plan/timetable in accomplishing the performance task (e.g. checklist, calendar of activities)	4.03	O
2.4 Prepare needed materials for the activity	4.16	O
2.5 Read and understand the scoring guide before working on the task	3.8	S
3. Individual Activity. (Lens Ray Diagramming); Construct ray diagrams to locate and describe the		

image formed by a thin lens at different positions of the object from the lens.		
3.1 Re-read the self-learning module	4.19	O
3.2 Read and understand the instructions/ procedures in accomplishing the individual activity	3.56	O
3.3 Prepare a plan/timetable in accomplishing the performance task (e.g. checklist, calendar of activities)	3.99	O
3.4 Prepare needed materials for the activity	4.08	O
3.5 Read and understand the scoring guide before working on the task	4.21	A
4. Individual Task: Simple Experiment: Describing images characteristics produced by spherical mirrors		
4.1 Read and understand the instructions/ procedures in accomplishing the individual activity	3.66	O
4.2 Prepare a plan/timetable in accomplishing the performance task (e.g. checklist, calendar of activities)	3.98	O
4.3 Prepare needed materials for the activity	3.35	O
4.4 Record the observations/ data made or gathered while doing the experiment	4.06	O
4.5 Read and understand the scoring guide before working on the task	3.83	O
Average Mean	3.79	O

Table 6
Mean Score on Science Virtual Activities in terms of Competencies Week 8 Synchronous

Week 8 Competency: Identify ways in which the properties of mirrors and lenses determine their use in optical instruments (e.g., cameras and binoculars)	<i>Student</i>	
	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Review on the properties of mirrors and mirrors and their uses in optical instruments		
1.1 Study the previous topic related to the properties	3.86	O

of mirrors and mirrors and their uses in optical instruments	3.64	O
1.2 Highlight the important concept and information about the topic in the module	3.23	S
1.3 Answer review questions given by our teacher promptly	2.85	S
1.4 Write a summary of what I remember and learned about the topic	3.15	S
1.5 Present the things I learned about the topic using graphic organizers and/or illustrations (e.g. charts, tables, matrix, graphs etc.)		
2. Lecture/Discussion on The properties of mirrors	3.78	O
and lenses and their use in optical instruments	2.98	S
2.1 Read the assigned topic about the in advance from the module		
2.2 Study the materials (e.g. video clips, Powerpoint presentations) uploaded/sent by our teacher in advance	3.58	O
2.3 Read other books and materials about the topic	2.97	S
2.4 Jot down notes and questions	3.17	S
2.5 Organize my notes using illustrations and/or graphic organizers	4.19	O
2.6 Note ideas, points, and concepts I do not understand and ask them to my teacher for clarification	3.84	O
3. Video Analysis on the properties of mirrors and mirrors and their uses in optical instruments	3.58	O
3.1 Watch the video silently;	3.56	O
3.2 Jots down notes and information about the topic;	2.82	S
3.3 Answer questions given by the teacher;	3.94	O
3.4 Participate during the discussion of the video		
3.5 Ask questions about the video viewed	3.79	O
4. Close Reading Activity on the properties of mirrors	3.75	O
and mirrors and their uses in optical instruments	3.07	S
4.1 Read the assigned silently		
4.2 Note/ highlight specific words or phrases found in the text	3.28	S
4.3 Answer text-dependent/ comprehension questions based on my understanding of the text	3.73	O

4.4 Outline the content of the text using graphic organizers		
4.5 Annotate the assigned text with main ideas, questions, or comments		
Average Mean	3.47	O

Table 7
Mean Score on Science Virtual Activities in terms of
Competencies Week 8 Asynchronous

Week 8 Competency: Identify ways in which the properties of mirrors and lenses determine their use in optical instruments (e.g., cameras and binoculars)	<i>Student</i>	
	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Activity Sheets the properties of mirrors and mirrors and their uses in optical instruments based from the SLM		
1.1 Read the instructions in each activity carefully	4.28	A
1.2 Re-read the self-learning module	3.5	O
1.3 Review notes about the topic	3.75	O
1.4 Clarify misunderstood instructions and/or parts of the activity to the teacher	3.23	S
1.5 Check my answers against the given answer key/ key to correction included in the module	3.02	S
2. Video Presentation on the properties of mirrors and mirrors and their uses in optical instruments		
2.1 Re-read the self-learning module to review about the topic	3.69	O
2.2 Read and understand the instructions/ procedures in creating the video	4.01	O
2.3 Prepare a plan/timetable in accomplishing the performance task (e.g. checklist, calendar of activities)	3.53	O
2.4 Prepare needed materials and tools in creating the video (e.g. script, video recording and editing tools)	3.89	O
2.5 Read and understand the scoring guide/criteria before working on the video	4.16	A
Average Mean	3.70	O

Table 8

**Summary Table on Mean Scores of Competencies
in Science Virtual Activities**

Indicators	Grand Mean	Interpretation
Synchronous		
Week 5	3.66	O
Week 6 - 7		
Week 8	3.88	O
Asynchronous	3.47	O
Week 5		
Week 6 - 7		
Week 8	4.08	O
	3.79	O
	3.70	O

Table 9

Significant Difference on the Competencies in Science Virtual Activities

Indicator	Critical Values	Computed Value	Interpretation	Decision
Synchronous	3.03	0.39	Not significant	Accepted Ho
Asynchronous	3.03	0.43	Not significant	Accepted Ho

Level of Significance: 0.05

Table 10

**Significant Relationship between Students' Profile and Competencies
in Science Virtual Activities- Synchronous**

	Computed r-value	Interpretation	Ho Remarks	Decision
Age	-0.06	Negligible Correlation	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Sex	0.10	Negligible Correlation	Not Significant	Accept Ho

Grade for Second Quarter	-0.22	Negligible Correlation	Not Significant	Accept Ho
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Table 11
Significant Relationship between Students' Profile Competencies
in Science Virtual Activities- Asynchronous

	Computed r-value	Interpretation	Ho Remarks	Decision
Age	-0.12	Negligible Correlation	Not significant	Accept Ho
Sex	0.15	Negligible Correlation	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Grade for Second Quarter	-0.21	Negligible Correlation	Not Significant	Accept Ho

DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex and Grade for Second Quarter. In terms of age, 49 (49%) of the respondents were 16 years old, 45 (45%) of the respondents were 15 years old and 6 (6%) of the respondents were 17 years old. data disclosed the majority of the students were at the appropriate age as Grade 10 students. They are in their adolescent stage. When it comes to learning, these age groups manifest scientific thinking who show the ability to think abstractly. Sage (2015) explained in adolescence, hypothetico-deductive reasoning is manifested by learners which allows them,, test hypotheses using deductive reasoning allowing them to form logical conclusions about concepts they learn.

Relative to sex, 49 (49%) were male and 51 (51%) were female. Majority of the students were female. The sex variable is assumed to have effect on the assessment of the students towards the virtual activities. Since the results showed dominance of female students in the setting of the study, it is assumed that this may influence the reception and assessment of the students toward synchronous and asynchronous activities. The study of Malik et. al. (2017) revealed a dominance of female students as participants determining their preferences to use synchronous and asynchronous platforms and resources. The results showed a statistical difference in students' responses regarding the effectiveness of synchronous and asynchronous activities. Male students preferred both synchronous and asynchronous activities more than the female students. Moreover,

the students showed greater interest in synchronous activities when they received immediate credits, recognition, and grades.

In terms of grades for the second quarter, there were 56 (56 followed by 21 (21%) having the grades of 91-100 that belongs to outstanding and 19 (19%) with grades ranging from 76-80 which is satisfactory and 4 (4%) having 75 and below which are satisfactory. Among the demographic profile in terms of age most of the respondents were 16 years old. In the study conducted to determine the readiness of grade 10 students of Molugan National High School to enroll in the Accountancy, Business and Management strand of the Senior High School curriculum. The result showed that 16 years old is the ideal age for grade 10. The eldest age of the respondents are 18 years old (Bation and Sabudana 2018).

In terms of sex, majority were female, and majority of the respondents' grades range from 81-90 which are very satisfactory.

Table 2 presents the mean score on Science Virtual Activities in terms of competencies for Week 5 in the synchronous class, its weighted mean and verbal interpretation. Under review on the effects of EM radiation on living things and the environment, the first sub-indicator studies the previous topic related to EM radiation had a weighted mean of 3.55 and interpreted as often. Highlighting the important concept and information about the topic in the module had 4.07 weighted mean and interpreted as often. Similarly, answer review questions given by our teacher promptly got 3.65. Both write a summary of what I remember and learned about the topic and present the things I learned about the topic using graphic organizers and/or illustrations (e.g. charts, tables, matrix, graphs etc.) had a weighted mean of 3.2 and 3.12 consecutively and with verbal interpretation of sometimes.

For this indicator the results showed that most of the students highlighted important concepts since the teacher conducts assessment in the form of graded recitations or quizzes during review time. but not everyone reviewed their materials because not everyone made a summary of what they learned therefore not everyone was able to present what they learned through graphic organizers or illustrations. The study of Jansen et. al (2017) affirmed the findings presented in the indicator pointing out that students frequently engage in notetaking to improve the amount of information they remember from lectures. Indeed, one beneficial effect of note taking is known as the encoding effect, which refers to deeper processing of information because of taking notes.

Under the second indicator lecture/discussion on the Effect of EM radiation on living the environment, read the assigned topic about the in advance had a weighted mean of 3.05 with verbal interpretation of sometimes, study the materials (e.g. video clips, powerpoint presentations) uploaded/sent by our teacher in advance obtained a weighted mean of 3.88 and interpreted as often. Reading other books and materials about the topic garnered a weighted mean of 3.02 and interpreted as sometimes. Jot down notes and questions had a weighted mean of 3.67 having an interpretation of often. Lastly, organize my notes using illustrations and/or graphic organizers got a weighted mean of 3.08 and

note ideas, points, and concepts I do not understand and ask them to my teacher for clarification had a weighted mean of 3.2 and interpreted as sometimes

Since the instructional materials used are digitized students' interests were aroused, engaging them to search and read for other references. The findings of the study congruently jived the ideas of (Butcher et. al 2017) that digitized objects facilitated key critical thinking processes, particularly observation, problem finding, elaboration and evaluation. Student feedback was very positive and focused on strong interest .

The findings of the study entitled “Using digitized objects to promote critical thinking and engagement in classrooms” shows that digitized objects facilitated key critical thinking processes, particularly observation, problem finding, elaboration and evaluation. Student feedback was very positive and focused on strong interest in 3D technologies and the ability to engage in authentic exploration. Observations showed very high levels of on-task engagement (Butcher et. al 2017).

The third indicator video analysis on the effects of EM radiation on living things and the environment having five sub-indicators obtained the following results: watch the video silently obtaining 4.38 weighted mean and interpreted as always. Jots down notes and information about the topic got a weighted mean of 3.86 and answer questions given by the teacher had a weighted mean of 3.63 interpreted as often. In addition, participate during the discussion of the video and ask questions about the video viewed obtained a weighted mean of 2.55 and with verbal interpretation of sometimes.

Students can somehow participate during discussion since they were able to jot down important notes and information about the topic. During video analysis sometimes the teacher causes sudden interruption while pausing the video and conducts a quick discussion in some part of the video. Similarly, Hong & Riper (2016) stressed the importance of creating a guided discourse structure for viewing videos pointing out to give valuable organization to the video analysis.

With regards to the fourth indicator with five sub-indicators close reading activity on the effects of EM radiation on living things and the environment, read the assigned activity silently got a weighted mean of 4.31 with verbal interpretation of always. Note/ highlight specific words or phrases found in the text gained a weighted mean of 4.03 with verbal interpretation of often. Answer text-dependent/ comprehension questions based on my understanding of the text and outline the content of the text using graphic organizers got a verbal interpretation of sometimes and a weighted mean of 3.08 and 3.32, consecutively. Lastly, annotate the assigned text with main ideas, questions, or comments had 4.46 weighted mean and interpreted as always.

Students were given appropriate material for close reading activity, with detailed instructions therefore students were able to follow instructions such as highlighting important phrases, answering questions, outline contents and annotate the main ideas of the text. The results found in this indicator affirmed the ideas of Jansen et al (2017) highlighting that students expressed satisfaction with the close reading instructional

routine as implemented which might facilitate student buy-in overtime and with increased engagement leading to better results. The results found in this indicator affirmed the ideas of Jansen et al (2017) highlighting that students expressed satisfaction with the close reading instructional routine as implemented which might facilitate student buy-in overtime and with increased engagement leading to better results. Further, Table 2 revealed that the average mean score on Science virtual activities in terms of competencies for Week 5 of synchronous class were sometimes having 3.66 weighted mean as rated by the participants.

Table 3 exhibits the mean score on Science virtual activities in terms of competencies for Week 5 in the asynchronous class with its corresponding weighted mean and verbal interpretation. Under the activity sheets based on the SLM on the effects of EM radiation, four indicators obtained a verbal interpretation of often with the following weighted mean: read the instructions in each activity carefully with 3.55, re-read the self-learning module having 3.83, review notes about the topic obtaining 3.41 and check my answers against the given answer key/ key to correction included in the module got 3.64. The sub-indicator clarifies misunderstood instructions and/or parts of the activity to the teacher that had a weighted mean of 3.08 and interpreted as sometimes.

For this indicator, the result shows that the students are still performing asynchronous tasks even without the teachers, but some of the students are not asking the teacher for any clarification about misunderstood instructions in the activity. Students are directly looking for information on the internet, others ask their classmates for better comprehension. Kaur & Sidhu (2019) affirmed the findings in this indicator that students lacked the confidence needed to learn autonomously. Moreover, it was reiterated that students needed help in organizing, monitoring and evaluating their learning. If students are required to participate in asynchronous online learning, necessary steps must be taken to ensure they are empowered with the necessary skills and tools to help them manage their own learning for their journey to become lifelong autonomous learners.

The second indicator performance task: provide examples of useful instruments or devices that use EM waves and identify its advantages and disadvantages. Only re-read the self-learning module got 4.26 and interpreted as always. The rest of the four indicators had a verbal interpretation of often with its corresponding weighted mean read and understand the instructions/ procedures in accomplishing the activity with 3.58, prepare a plan/timetable in accomplishing the performance task (e.g. checklist, calendar of activities) with a weighted mean of 3.91, prepare needed materials for the activity with 4.15 and 3.84 weighted mean for read and understand the scoring guide before working on the task.

Since the activity is a performance task students focus on reading the module in order to plan the procedures and prepare the things needed such as materials to be used to perform the task properly. Thus, Rheman and Syeda (2021) mentioned that e-learning improves independent learning ability and self-regulating thinking more than the traditional learning modes. In general Table 3 showed that the average mean score on

Science virtual activities in terms of competencies for Week 5 of asynchronous class were rated as often having 4.08 weighted mean as rated by the participants.

Table 4 demonstrates the mean score on Science virtual activities in terms of competencies for Week 6-7 in the synchronous class with its corresponding weighted mean and verbal interpretation. Under the review on the qualitative characteristics of images formed by plane and curved mirrors and lenses, four indicators obtained a verbal interpretation of sometimes with the following weighted mean: study the previous topic related to qualitative characteristics of images formed by plane and curved mirrors and lenses having a weighted mean of 4.06, answer review questions given by our teacher promptly with 3.26, write a summary of what I remember and learned about the topic had 2.87 and present the things I learned about the topic using graphic organizers and/or illustrations with a weighted mean of 3.14. Lastly, the sub-indicator highlighted the important concept and information about the topic in the module garnered a weighted mean of 3.63 and verbal interpretation often.

For this indicator the results showed that most of the students highlighted important concepts but not everyone reviewed their materials because not everyone made a summary of what they learned therefore not everyone was able to present what they learned through graphic organizers or illustrations. Given the results found in the indicator, Torre Franca, et al (2022) emphasized that student achievement can be enhanced by using graphic organizers and other non-traditional instructional strategies. Further, the study highlighted that graphic organizers have positive effects upon student learning.

The second indicator lecture /discussion on the qualitative characteristics (orientation, type, and magnification) of images formed by plane and curved mirrors and lenses having six sub-indicators revealed the following results: reading the assigned topic in advance from the module got a weighted mean of 3.88 interpreted as often. Studying the materials (e.g. video clips, PowerPoint presentations) uploaded/sent by our teacher in advance had a mean of 2.87 and interpreted as sometimes. Read other books and materials about the topic got a mean of 3.69 interpreted as often. Both jot down notes and questions and organize my notes using illustrations and/or graphic organizers got a weighted mean of 2.96 and 3.23 consecutively and interpreted as sometimes. Lastly, note ideas, points, and concepts I do not understand and ask my teacher for clarification to obtain a weighted mean of 3.89 interpreted as often.

Before discussion was proper almost everyone read in advance the self-learning modules and other references due to the teacher's instruction, but only a few students studied in advance the uploaded instructional materials such as PowerPoint presentations and videos due to lack of instruction. Moreover, only a few ask the teacher for clarification about the concept they do not understand because of this not everyone can organize notes using illustrations or graphic organizers. The results derived from the indicator affirmed the idea of Garcia (2018) emphasizing that engaging with the material before class, class time can be spent on more challenging activities with feedback from the instructor and classmates. In addition, pre-class activities can be a challenge for

students, who often do not have the skills necessary to critically engage with the assigned reading/viewing tasks. As a result, students often come to class under-prepared despite completing the pre-class activities.

The third indicator video analysis on Video Analysis on the qualitative characteristics of images formed by plane and curved mirrors and lenses having five sub-indicators obtained the following results: watch the video silently, jots down notes and information about the topic and answer questions given by the teacher had a weighted mean of 3.89, 3.64 and 3.64, respectively and interpreted as often. Moreover, participants during the discussion of the video had a weighted mean of 2.79 interpreted as sometimes and asked questions about the video viewed got 4.25 weighted mean interpreted as always.

Majority of the students watched the video attentively while jotting down important information, therefore they were able to answer the questions given by the teachers and ask questions in return, Making the discussion more interactive since the students are participative. The results conferred the study of (Ou, Joyner, & Goel, 2019.) that the video lectures were informative and easy to understand and that the video lessons were valuable in helping the students to learn.

Relative to the fourth indicator close reading Activity on the qualitative characteristics of images formed by plane and curved mirrors and lenses with five sub-indicators, read the assigned activity silently and note/ highlight specific words or phrases found in the text gained a weighted mean of 3.75 and 3.85 consecutively with verbal interpretation often. On the other hand, answer text-dependent/ comprehension questions based on my understanding of the text and outline the content of the text using graphic organizers got a verbal interpretation of sometimes and a weighted mean of 2.99 and 3.35, sequentially. Lastly, annotate the assigned text with main ideas, questions, or comments had 4.42 weighted mean and interpreted as always.

Students' specific words or phrases found in the text gained the lowest among all sub indicators which further affirmed Storm, et.al (2015) that students, possibly owing to limited available study time, engage in massed re-readings or study sessions. In such situations, students could probably improve the effectiveness of their study via selective highlighting because such practice would lead them to think about why they initially selected certain words or phrases to highlight, resulting in deeper processing during subsequent readings.

Further, Table 4 revealed that the average mean score on Science virtual activities in terms of competencies for Week 6-7 of asynchronous class were rated as often having 3.88 weighted mean as rated by the participants.

Table 5 highlights the mean Score on Science Virtual Activities in terms of competencies for Week 6-7 in asynchronous class with its weighted mean and verbal interpretation. Under the activity sheets on the qualitative characteristics (orientation, type, and magnification) of images formed by plane and curved mirrors and lenses based

from the SLM, the first two sub-indicators read the instructions in each activity carefully and re-read the self-learning module had a weighted mean of 3.66 and 3.65 and interpreted as often. The next two sub-indicators review notes about the topic and clarify misunderstood instructions and/or parts of the activity to the teacher were interpreted as sometimes with the weighted mean 3.17 and 2.97, respectively. Lastly, check my answers against the key to correction included in the module obtained 3.78 interpreted as often.

For this indicator, the result shows that the students are still performing the assigned asynchronous task without the teachers, but some of the students are not asking the teacher for any clarification about misunderstood instructions in the activity. The derived results jived the ideas of Gao (2020) that less opportunity for interaction with the instructor would diminish students' learning passion and motivation. Although they are focusing on learning, students may not fully understand the materials simply through self-learning. In addition, it was emphasized that to create a supportive classroom environment in an asynchronous learning environment, instructors should arrange office hours to answer questions. Group projects could be assigned to encourage peer collaboration and interaction, to reduce students' sense of social isolation.

Under the second indicator collaborative activity: create a video presentation of images produced by spherical mirrors and lenses and their uses in daily life, four sub-indicators obtained the following results: re-read the self-learning module had a weighted mean of 4.13, read and understand the instructions/ procedures in accomplishing the collaborative activity with 3.72 weighted mean, a weighted mean of 4.03 for prepare a plan/timetable in accomplishing the performance task (e.g. checklist, calendar of activities) and prepare needed materials for the activity got a weighted mean of 4.16. The four sub-indicators were interpreted as often. Lastly, read and understand the scoring guide before working on the task garnered a weighted mean of 3.8 and interpreted as sometimes.

Since the activity is a group performance task students focus on reading the module in order to plan the procedures and prepare the things needed such as materials to be used to perform the task properly and develop the output required by the teacher,

In consonance, Stephens and Roberts (2019) in their study stressed the importance of group work collaboration that it prepares the students to reach the expectations of 21st century workplaces, both in terms of interpersonal and technical skills. In addition, students have an opportunity to demonstrate their individual and collective abilities through authentic assessments on group assignments and activities and build upon feedback provided by their peers.

The third indicator focusing on individual activity (Lens Ray Diagramming) and construct ray diagrams to locate and describe the image formed by a thin lens at different positions of the object from the lens, four indicators were interpreted as often and garnered the following weighted mean: re-read the self-learning module with 4.19 weighted mean, read and understand the instructions/procedures in accomplishing the collaborative activity had 3.56, prepare a plan/timetable in accomplishing the performance

task (e.g. checklist, calendar of activities) garnered a weighted mean of 3.99 and 4.08 weighted mean to prepare needed materials for the activity. The last sub-indicator read and understand the scoring guide before working on the task and 4.21 weighted mean interpreted as always.

The activity requires individual output, the result shows that the students did not read and understand the instructions/procedure in accomplishing the task. The problem viewed among the students in this treatise was also highlighted by Jaroslawska, et.al (2016) that the ability to follow instructions successfully is vital for effective cognitive functioning. Moreover, following instructions through to successful completion requires simultaneously holding in mind the detailed content of the sequence while monitoring ongoing performance. This capacity to maintain information while engaged in other cognitive activities is a key feature of working memory.

Relative to the fourth indicator on individual task: simple experiment: describing images characteristics produced by spherical mirrors with five sub-indicators, all the sub-indicators were interpreted as often garnering the following weighted mean: read and understand the instructions/ procedures in accomplishing the individual activity with 3.66, prepare a plan/timetable in accomplishing the performance task (e.g. checklist, calendar of activities) with 3.98, prepare needed materials for the activity got 3.35, record the observations/ data made or gathered while doing the experiment with 4.06 and read and understand the scoring guide before working on the task with 3.83 weighted mean.

Since activity requires individual output, the result shows that the students are thoroughly prepared by reading the self-learning module, by understanding the procedures and scoring guide as well as preparing the materials needed for the activity. Preparation of materials got the lowest mean, maybe because of the availability of the identified materials to be used indicated in the activity sheets.

Meanwhile, Table 5 revealed that the average mean score on Science virtual activities in terms of competencies for Week 6-7 of asynchronous class were rated as often having 3.79 weighted mean as rated by the participants.

Table 6 exhibits the mean Score on Science Virtual Activities in terms of competencies for Week 8 in synchronous class with its weighted mean and verbal interpretation. Under the review on the properties of mirrors and mirrors and their uses in optical instruments with five sub-indicators, study the previous topic related to the properties of mirrors and mirrors and their uses in optical instruments and highlight the important concept and information about the topic in the module got a weighted mean of 3.86 and 3.64 interpreted as often. The remaining three sub-indicators answer review questions given by our teacher promptly had a weighted mean of 3.23, write a summary of what I remember and learned about the topic with 2.85 and present the things I learned about the topic using graphic organizers and/or illustrations (e.g. charts, tables, matrix, graphs etc.) with 3.15 were interpreted as sometimes.

For this indicator the results showed that most of the students highlighted important concepts but not everyone reviewed their materials because not everyone made a summary of what they learned therefore not everyone was able to present what they learned through graphic organizers or illustrations. The second indicator on lecture/discussion on the properties of mirrors and lenses and their use in optical instrument with six sub-indicators had the following results: read the assigned topic about the in advance from the module, read other books and materials about the topic and note ideas, points, and concepts I do not understand and ask them to my teacher for clarification obtained a weighted mean of 3.78, 3.58 and 4.19, consecutively and interpreted as often. On the other hand, the remaining three were interpreted as sometimes obtaining the following weighted mean: study the materials (e.g. video clips, PowerPoint presentations) uploaded/sent by our teacher in advance with 2.98 weighted mean, jot down notes and questions having 2.97 and organize my notes using illustrations and/or graphic organizers having a weighted mean of 3.17.

Before discussion proper almost everyone read in advance the self-learning modules and other references due to the teacher's instruction, but only a few students studied in advance the uploaded instructional materials such as PowerPoint presentations and videos due to lack of instruction. The results reveal that an instructor's course preparation is significantly positively related to the students (Yang and Ching, 2015) viewing activities, while instructor's guidance and assistance has a significant impact on the students' completing learning tasks. The study also indicates that the students' viewing activities have a direct positive influence on their completing learning tasks activities. Students' completing learning tasks exert direct positive influence on their interaction for learning, while their viewing activities have an indirect impact on their interaction activities. Moreover, only a few ask the teacher for clarification about the concept they do not understand and for this reason not everyone can organize notes using illustrations or graphic organizers.

The third indicator focusing on video analysis on the properties of mirrors and mirrors and their uses in optical instruments garnered the following results: watch the video silently had a weighted mean of 3.84, jots down notes and information about the topic with 3.58, answer questions given by the teacher with 3.56 and ask questions about the video viewed with 3.94 computed weighted mean. Thus, the four sub-indicators can be interpreted as often. Only sub-indicators participate during the discussion with 2.82 weighted mean interpreted as sometimes.

Majority of the students watched the video attentively while jotting down important information, (Richtberg and Gurwitz 2019) pointed out in multimedia learning and the active processing assumption learning that videos should be more interactive to foster an active processing of the presented information. In addition, it should include tasks related to the presented content (at the end of the video or integrated) because it seems advantageous to make learning videos more interactive by including tasks directly in the video. According to (Richtberg and Gurwidz 2019) learning videos should be more interactive to encourage active processing of the content. This can be achieved by including tasks either at the end of the video or integrated throughout it. By doing so,

students can respond to questions posed by teachers and ask their own questions, making the discussion more engaging and interactive.

The fourth indicator focused on close reading activity on the properties of mirrors and mirrors and their uses in optical instruments. The following sub-indicators were categorized as often having its weighted mean that follows: read the assigned silently with 3.79, note/ highlight specific words or phrases found in the text with 3.75 and annotate the assigned text with main ideas, questions, or comments obtaining 3.73. On the other hand, the remaining two sub-indicators, answer text-dependent/ comprehension questions based on my understanding of the text, got 3.07 and outline the content of the text using graphic organizers with 3.28 weighted were interpreted as sometimes.

Students were given appropriate material for close reading activity with detailed instructions, The result showed that among the sub indicator answer text-dependent/ comprehension questions based on my understanding of the text, got the lowest among all other sub indicators some of the students have difficulty understanding the instructions, pre-reading activity and exposure to definitions of difficult words in the text prior to reading seem to have resulted in better comprehension in addition although pre-reading activities, especially those that provide background knowledge, assist students increasing text comprehension, these activities are under the teacher's control rather than the students (Salehi and Abbaszadeh 2015).

Thus, Table 6 disclosed that the average mean score on Science virtual activities in terms of competencies for Week 8 of synchronous class were rated as often having 3.47 weighted mean as rated by the participants.

Table 7 exhibits the mean score on Science virtual activities in terms of competencies for Week 8 in asynchronous class with its corresponding weighted mean and verbal interpretation. Under the activity sheets the properties of mirrors and mirrors and their uses in optical instruments based from the SLM, read the instructions in each activity carefully got a weighted mean of 4.28 interpreted as always. It is followed by re-read the self-learning module and review notes about the topic having a weighted mean of 3.50 and 3.75 and interpreted as often. The remaining two indicators clarify misunderstood instructions and/or parts of the activity to the teacher got 3.23 and check my answers against the given answer key/ key to correction included in the module had 3.02 weighted mean and interpreted as sometimes.

For this indicator, the result shows that the students are still performing the assigned asynchronous task without the teachers, that Self-learning requires the student to maintain self-discipline, which can be difficult without direct supervision from the teacher. Poor interaction between learners and facilitators, and a lack of clarity of the purpose and goals of the learning can impede the learning process. Moreover, students' maturity might increase their degree of self-discipline, Bączek et al (2021) which is consistent with findings in this study. some of the students are not asking the teacher for any clarification about misunderstood instructions in the activity. Students are directly

looking for information on the internet, others ask their classmates for better comprehension.

The observation seen in the study of Kintu et al (2017) that teacher presence in face-to-face sessions lessens psychological distance between them and the learners and leads to greater learning. This is because there are verbal aspects like giving praise, soliciting viewpoints, humor, etc and non-verbal expressions like eye contact, facial expressions, gestures, etc which make teachers to be closer to learners psychologically

For challenges, students experienced social isolation in an asynchronous distance learning environment. To be specific, they had less opportunity for class communication and discussion. They also did not know their peers' learning progress. Thus, they experienced a distance from others which demotivates their learning passion. Along with this line, they considered interaction to be another challenge in asynchronous online courses because they were not able to ask the instructor questions then received right away feedback. Furthermore, some students noted that they did not fully understand the learning content through self-learning (Lin and Gao 2020).

The second indicator focused on video presentation on the properties of mirrors and mirrors and their uses in optical instruments. Only read and understand the scoring guide/criteria got 4.16 and interpreted as always. The rest of the four indicators had a verbal interpretation of often with its corresponding weighted mean re-read the self-learning module to review about the topic had 3.69, read and understand the instructions/procedures in creating the video with 4.01, prepare a plan/timetable in accomplishing the performance task (e.g. checklist, calendar of activities) had 3.53 and prepare needed materials and tools in creating the video (e.g. script, video recording and editing tools) having a weighted mean of 3.89.

In general Table 7 showed that the average mean score on Science virtual activities in terms of competencies for Week 8 of asynchronous class were rated as often having 3.70 weighted mean as rated by the participants.

Table 8 highlights the summary of mean scores of competencies in Science virtual activities in synchronous and asynchronous classes. In terms of synchronous class, Week 5 garnered a weighted mean of 3.66 and interpreted as often. Week 6-7 had a mean of 3.88 and interpreted as often. A mean of 3.47 and verbal interpretation of often was obtained in activities in Week 8. On the other hand, in asynchronous class, Week 5 obtained a weighted mean of 4.08 and verbal interpretation of often. Week 6-7 obtained a weighted mean of 3.79 and verbal interpretation of often. Week 8 garnered a weighted mean of 3.70 having a verbal interpretation of often.

The table shows that in Week 5 a weighted mean of 4.8 and verbal interpretation often was garnered and the leading among the grand mean in asynchronous because the students enjoyed conducting simple experiments given during this week. It was followed by Week 6-7 with a weighted mean of 3.79 and verbal interpretation often. The results obtained were out of the interactive activities given during this week such as virtual group

collaboration with a video output. Lastly, for Week 8 it has a weighted mean of 3.70 and a verbal interpretation often where there are a limited number of activities during this week due to time constraint.

Despite the widespread concern that students will have difficulty managing their time in online courses with high levels of student freedom, this study found that most learners were very effective in their learning strategies. The findings speak well for the potential of distance education environments to provide high quality self-paced learning, accommodating different learning strategies, which is difficult to do in group-paced courses as supported by Del Valle and Duffy (2016).

For synchronous, Week 6-7 was the leading among the other weeks with weighted mean of 3.88 and verbal interpretation often because the given activities during this week are interactive such as video analysis and virtual collaboration that happens real time. It was followed by Week 5 with a weighted mean of 3.66 and verbal interpretation often. Lastly, Week 8 obtained a weighted mean of 3.47 and a verbal interpretation often, the same as asynchronous, the number of activities for the week was limited.

In consonance with the results, Balasubramanian (2015) stressed that younger students preferred interactive learning, such as: live chats and group projects. This net generation is portrayed as embracing the interactivity and immediacy of online communications.

In addition, Lebenicnik, et al (2016) indicated that among all students, activities with lower demands for engagement are most common. Some differences were observed between student teachers and students from other programs. Student teachers were more likely than their peers to perform certain activities aimed at meeting diverse learner needs, but the percentage of students performing more advanced activities was higher for students in other study programs than for student teachers. The categorization of activities revealed that student teachers are less likely to undertake activities that involve interaction with others. Among the sample student teachers, it was found that personal innovation is correlated with diversity of activities in only one category. The results showed that student teachers should be encouraged to perform more advanced activities, especially activities involving interaction with others, collaborative learning and use of ICT to plan and organize their own learning processes.

Table 9 shows the significant difference in the competencies in Science virtual activities in synchronous and asynchronous classes. The findings of the study revealed the result that in synchronous a computed F-value of 0.39 which was less than the critical-value of 3.03. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the virtual synchronous activities in Science for the three identified learning competencies. On the other hand, the asynchronous class obtained a computed F-value 0.43 which was lower than the critical F-value 3.03. Thus, it can be interpreted as no significant difference among the virtual activities in Science in terms of the three identified competencies. That led to the acceptance of the null hypothesis this means that there is no significant

difference on virtual activities for the second quarter in terms of synchronous and asynchronous.

As indicated in Table 8 summary of mean scores of competencies in science virtual activities all indicators presented closely related grand mean and share the same interpretation often. The results show that the students answered the same, on how they accomplish the activities in both synchronous and asynchronous virtual activities. Perhaps the reason for the result is the attitude of the student towards the importance of learning. Based on the profile of the respondent, 56% possess a very satisfactory grade.

The relationship between different demographics for learner characteristics and found strong connections. Grade point average was found to have the strongest connection. This is not surprising that those with a stronger GPA in other classes also appear to do well in online classes (Wojciechowski, & Palmer, 2015).

In addition, Studies indicate that student characteristics such as Learner attitudes to blended learning can result in its effectiveness and these shape behavioral intentions which usually lead to persistence in a learning environment, blended inclusive. Selim, (2007) cited by Kintu et al (2017) noted that the learners' attitude towards e-learning and blended learning are success factors for these learning environments.

Table 10 reveals the significant relationship between students' profile and competencies in Science Virtual Activities in synchronous class. In terms of age, a computed r-value of -0.06 was obtained at -0.058 level of significance. Therefore, there is no significant relationship between age and competencies in Science Virtual Activities in synchronous class. This implies that the null hypothesis is accepted. Majority of the student-respondents is 16 years old all activities given for their grade level are age appropriate. affirmed by the study conducted Bation and Sabudana (2018) to determine the readiness of grade 10 students of Molugan National High School to enroll in the Accountancy, Business and Management strand of the Senior High School curriculum. The result showed that 16 years old is the ideal age for grade 10.

Relative to sex, a computed r-value of 0.10 was garnered revealing that there is no significant relationship between sex and competencies in Science Virtual activities in synchronous The synchronous virtual activities are suited for both male and female Grade 10 students. Most of the activities administered for synchronous sessions are collaborative. The effect of gender grouping mainly influences students' attitudes, rather than performance. Moreover, Gender differences mainly exist on attitude rather than learning achievement (Zhan et al 2015). Moreover, a computed r-value of -0.22 was obtained exhibiting that there is no significant relationship between grade for second quarter and competencies in Science Virtual activities in synchronous class. As shown in the results, negligible correlation was found between students' profile and competencies in Science Virtual Activities in synchronous class which leads to the acceptance of null hypothesis. The second quarter grade is determined by different components such as written works and performance tasks. Virtual activities are categorized under performance tasks thus this is not only the main components of the grade but also the computation of

the score obtained in the written works administered in other ways such as google forms and other online platforms for assessments.

Paul and Jefferson (2019) study that goal to determine which teaching method proved more effective over the 8-year period. The study evaluated the ability of course instructors to design the course for online delivery and develop various interactive multimedia models in environmental science. The result reveals that there is no significant difference in student performance of online learners. Overall, It only shows that there is no difference in the learning success of students enrolled in the online modality stating that “in terms of learning, students who apply themselves diligently should be successful in the online learning environment.

Table 11 exhibits the significant relationship between students’ profile and competencies in Science Virtual Activities in asynchronous class. In terms of age, a computed r-value of -0.12 was obtained at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there is no significant relationship between age and competencies in Science Virtual Activities in synchronous class Majority of the student-respondents is 16 years old all activities given for their grade level are age appropriate .affirmed by the study conducted Bation and Sabudana (2018) to determine the readiness of grade 10 students of Molugan National High School to enroll in the Accountancy, Business and Management strand of the Senior High School curriculum. The result showed that 16 years old is the ideal age for grade 10.

With regards to sex, a computed r-value of 0.15 was garnered revealing that there is no significant relationship between sex and competencies in Science Virtual activities in synchronous class. Most of the activities administered for asynchronous sessions are collaborative activities. Gender differences mainly exist on attitude rather than learning achievement. (Zhan et al 2015). The effect of gender grouping mainly influences students’ attitudes, rather than performance. Moreover, Gender differences mainly exist on attitude rather than learning achievement. Furthermore, a computed r-value of -0.21 was obtained displaying that there is no significant relationship between grade for second quarter and competencies in Science Virtual activities in synchronous class. As presented in the results, negligible correlation was found between students’ profile and competencies in Science Virtual Activities in synchronous class.

Lin and Jefferson (2019) study that goal to determine which teaching method proved more effective over the 8-year period. The study evaluated the ability of course instructors to design the course for online delivery and develop various interactive multimedia models in environmental science. The result reveals that there is no significant difference in student performance between online and face-to-face learners. overall, It only shows that there is no difference in the learning success of students enrolled in the online modality vs. F2F course, stating that “in terms of learning, students who apply themselves diligently should be successful in either format”;

Conclusions

Corollary to the findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Profile of the Respondents

Students. Majority of the respondents were female, comprising 51% whose age were 16 years old. In terms of second quarter grades, most of the respondents or 56% had a very satisfactory performance.

2. Virtual Activities for Second Quarter

Synchronous

In the review, Week 5 competency findings showed students often highlighted important concepts and information. For Week 6 - 7 and Week 8 Competency, both findings showed that students often study the previous topic related to qualitative characteristics of images formed by plane and curved mirrors and lenses.

In lecture, for Week 5 competency, the result exhibits that students-respondents often studied the materials uploaded by the teacher. On the other hand, the results obtained for Week 6 - 7 competency, students sometimes take note of ideas, points, and concepts they do not understand and ask the teacher for clarification. Lastly, for Week 8 take note of ideas, points, and concepts they do not understand and ask it to the teacher for clarification. With regards to the video analysis, Week 5 competency reveals that students often watched the video silently. The results obtained both for Week 6 - 7 and Week 8 competencies display the same result, students are always asking questions about the video. In the reading activities provided, Week 5 competency revealed that students are always reading the activity material silently while for Week 8 competency: reading the activity material silently is often done. In addition, Week 6 - 7 competency showed that students always annotate the assigned text with main ideas. questions or comments.

Asynchronous

In the activity sheets, both for Week 5 and 6-7 competencies, findings revealed that students often checked their answer with the provided key to correction. In terms of asking for clarification for misunderstood instruction in the activity, Week 5, 6 - 7 as well as Week 8 competency shared the same results that respondents answered sometimes.

Relative to the collaborative activity, it was indicated in the findings that in Week 5 competency students always re-read the self-learning module. For Week 6-7 competency, students often prepare needed materials for the activity. Lastly, for Week 8 competency students always read and understand the scoring guide/criteria before working on the activity.

For the individual activities, all procedures are often observed by students in accomplishing the task except for one which is reading and understanding scoring guide before working on the task that was always observed by the student-respondents.

Test of Significant Difference there is no significant difference between the virtual activities in Science in terms of the three identified competencies both in the synchronous and asynchronous class.

A moderate positive/negative correlation between age and competencies in Science virtual activities in synchronous class was revealed while a negligible correlation between sex and grade for second quarter and competencies in Science Virtual activities were obtained. On the other hand, a negligible correlation between age, sex and grade for second quarter and competencies in Science Virtual activities was found in asynchronous class.

Recommendations

In light of the salient findings and concrete conclusions derived from the study, the following are highly recommended to:

Future researchers May conduct a similar study on online distance learning focused in other areas such as assessments, and evaluation and monitoring of the students progress.

1. Analyze the teaching and learning process of the online distance learning to improve the evaluation method in the modality.
1. Develop guidelines on how to conduct an honest assessment that will be the basis of computing grades.
2. Conduct a similar study that involves other respondents such as teachers and parents.

Parents. Since stakeholders' participation is integral to total child development, parents' roles, and participation in providing guidance to the students in their study is of high significance. The following are suggested to the parents:

1. Implement a strict study time at home by following the Weekly Home Learning Plan
2. Provide a quality time communicating with their children. Dialogue between parents and children is very important. It is the responsibility of the parent to provide guidance and advice.
3. Communicate with teachers regularly to discuss problems of students in school in relation to their academic standing.

School administrator. Since the school head is one of the major figures implementing distance learning in terms of supervision on student services, instruction, curriculum, and assessment practices. The school heads are hereby encouraged by the following in recommendations:

1. Plan and formulate policy guidelines in providing technical assistance to teachers and students in terms of availability of virtual activities to be used by the teachers and students.
2. Provide strategic direction in the school system in the light of distance learning.
3. Revise policies and procedures and adjust with the current situation emphasizing the modifications in the BE-LCP.
4. Assess teaching methods used in online learning modality.
5. Oversee the operation of online distance learning.
6. Encourage teachers to create a sense of normalcy for students to provide students with a sense that they are still connected to the school community.
7. Offer training in flexible learning to teachers, parents, and community partners.
8. Encourage professional development for teachers that promotes understanding and adaption to the current distance learning practices.

Students. As the end-users and center of the educational process, their responses were the basis for instructional adjustments and curricular innovations, much attention and consideration with the study habits must be emphasized. The following are recommended to the students:

1. Develop a consistent study habit in school and at home which may be done by allotting definite time in their schedules for studying.
2. Enhance their skills in taking down note to further retain ideas, points, and concepts they do not understand.
3. Establish clear and open communication to their respective teachers for clarification most especially those who were in asynchronous classes.
4. Participate actively and ask questions about the activities during the discussion.
5. Utilize varied reading strategies when reading the lesson/ texts.
6. Familiarize with reading techniques such as summarizing, using graphic organizers, outlining etc. to show their understanding of the key concepts in the activities provided in both modalities.
7. Give emphasis or importance to the scoring guide before working on the task so that they may be guided with the whereabouts of the activities and for the ease of accomplishing the tasks.
8. Communicate with teachers regularly to discuss problems of students in school in relation to their academic standing.

Teachers. The role of a teacher in the distance education system is considerably different from that of a teacher in the conventional system. A clear perception of this difference is very essential to understand the range of functions performed by teachers in distance education system. The following are therefore suggested:

1. Provide instructional materials, and guidance for collaborative learning, interactive discussion groups, individual learning, and research.
2. Provide prompt and accurate feedback to students to facilitate learning most especially in asynchronous learning.

3. Guidance in meeting the requirements of activities /tasks so that students may accomplish it with ease.
4. Focus on instruction and assistance in solving problems and mastery of the competencies required by students to participate during online discussion.
5. Nurture social learning and collaboration in a virtual environment.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author declares that the research was conducted with full observance of all ethical guidelines and principles. Informed consent was sought from all respondents prior to participation, ensuring they were aware of the purpose and nature of the study. Respondents were assured of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences. Anonymity and confidentiality of all participants were maintained strictly during the entire research process to ensure privacy. No conflict of interest was involved in conducting this study, and every effort was made to avoid any form of bias in the interpretation of findings. All measures to avoid plagiarism strictly went for the results solely made purely on academics.

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